

THEORY AND PRACTICE OF DISTANCE LEARNING AND FOREIGN
LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the theory and practice of distance learning and foreign language teaching, many methods of advanced learning technology, to cover the diversity of world languages in the field of foreign language teaching, to study distance languages paradigms are described in detail.

Keywords: distance learning, advanced learning technology, advanced learning, transactional problems.

Introduction:

Distance education (hereinafter - DL) is a high-tech product of the scientific and technological revolution, which widely uses the idea of a marketing approach in serving students, which actively spreads it around the world. explains. Today, distance learning includes computer and Internet learning technologies. Modern technology is a link between interaction participants, students, and the teacher, and they are thousands of miles apart. The training is conducted in the corporate network, via the Internet, via e-mail and other modern means of communication.

According to foreign researchers, the majority of distance students are still over 25 years of age, working and wanting to deepen their professional knowledge without quitting. Distance education is suitable for teaching in almost all fields, both technical and humanitarian.

Literature analysis and methodology:

It is especially important that DL systems with the ability to place images, audio and video files into the course are very easy for data perception by interacting

participants in the learning process. They are perfectly integrated into the traditional education system, ie. Training can be entirely distance or partial. For example, lectures and tests are remote, and laboratory work - in direct contact with the subjects of interaction, and so on.

Much has been done in the field of foreign language teaching to cover the diversity of world languages, but there are constant attempts for new solutions that take into account the specific needs of language learners.

This article is based on our experience and desire to improve the implementation of three academic English language courses at the Faculty of Information Technology (FIT), the first university institution to introduce a distance education system in Serbia and traditionally offer curricula. and as distance learning.

Results:

The process of developing and implementing English language courses at FIT is a general course design, selection of teaching materials, technological and pedagogical processing of course materials, the role of the teacher, student support and motivation, performance appraisal, course perspective from the point of view of the main differences between the two methods of evaluation and delivery must be taken into account.

Among the many methods of advanced learning technology, there are not many that stand out as distance learning. Influenced by the recent rapid development of web technologies, researchers in the field of ICT and education are constantly striving to make maximum use of technological resources and make the best pedagogical use of them.

Another problem is the motivation of distance learning students. In case of English courses, which do not aim only at acquiring knowledge but also some skills, including communication skills, this problem seems to be the greatest. An extremely significant task of the teacher in preparing the material and implementing the course is how to retain a high level of interaction in the teaching (virtual) environment despite the limited direct contact. The key problem for the students, however,

remains the lack of opportunities for direct oral peer communication as well as with the teacher.

Discussion:

Critically examines the field of language distance learning, and this field often calls into question the way in which a narrow concept is developed as the development of language learning opportunities through technology. The first sections focus on issues of concept and definition, as well as theoretical and pedagogical perspectives in the field.

Within the emerging paradigms for distance language learning, the focus shifts from structural and organizational problems to problems related to learning opportunities. The next section discusses the choices and challenges of integrating technology into a distance learning environment, in particular, technology decisions in socio-cultural contexts, the development of new learning areas, and the use of online technologies. ” the contribution of low-end technologies and research areas. To alleviate this potential feeling of isolation of distance learning students and strengthen their sense of belonging to the group and the institution, sometimes they are given group problem-solving tasks, and the complete e-mail or chat correspondence is sent to the teacher. This is the area which will be given more attention in the future.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the study of students' contributions to distance learning is an important research path in this field, dealing with technology and the virtual learning environment, and it is the sixth chapter. the subject of lim. The two final sections identify future research directions and provide a number of conclusions about research and practice in distance language learning, as technology-mediated interactions reflect on our language learning and teaching processes is increasingly influencing our style.

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